

Digital Marketing plan for Google Merchandise Store

**Digital Marketing Analytics and Strategy
(DMAaS)**

University of Salford RKC Campus

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GOOGLE MERCHANDISE STORE DIGITAL MARKETING PLAN4

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Google Merchandise Store Digital Marketing Plan

1.0 Analysis of Google Merchandise Store

The store's internal capabilities are analysed to identify strengths and weaknesses (Tsaka, Kastelli, & Yannis, 2004), the store's external environment is analysed using PESTLE analysis to identify the opportunities and threats (Gupta, 2013), Porter's Five is used for the competitor analysis (Alberto, Aguilar-Medina, & Fernández-Caballero, 2018). These feed into the SWOT (Strength, weakness, opportunity and threat) analysis (Cadle, Paul, & Paul, 2010; Gupta, 2013).

1.1 Literature Review

Digital technologies have changed the way and environment in which businesses operate (Weber, 2009), causing companies to be more focused on the consumers when making strategic decisions regarding marketing (Deloitte Touche Tohmatsu Limited , 2014). Digital marketing involves the integration of various strategies on the web simultaneously, following a methodology to find clear objectives by making use of different tools and platforms. (Peter, Peter, Peter, & Freundt, 2014). A digital marketing strategy is termed effective based on analysis and impact measurement (Kannana & Hongshuang, 2017) , thus, it has become important to gather correct and current data about the entire business environment (Bala & Verma, 2018).

PESTLE is a tool for analysing current data about business environment (Heinze, Fletcher, & Rashid, 2016), it analyses the political, economic, social, technological, legal and environmental factors that impact a business (Kuo-Jui, Ming-Lang, & Chiuc, 2012), an understanding of these factors enable businesses to understand their potential customers and become proactive rather than reactive to industry trends (Brandsma, 2018) .To gain insight into competitive analysis of a business environment the porter's five forces model is applied (Kuo-Jui et al., 2012), developed by Michael Porter of Harvard Business school in 1979 (Roberta, 2019), it analyses the five

competitive forces closest to an organisation; current competition, new entrants, substitutes, buyers and suppliers, it postulates that a change in one of these factors requires an environmental reassessment for the business (Kuo-Jui et al. , 2012; Porter, 2008).

1.2 External Analysis

1.2.1 PESTLE Analysis of Google Merchandise Store.

1.2.1.1 Politics

Google merchandise store is an online store managed by Brand Addition Limited offering an array of google branded products to Africa, Asia, Australia, Canada, Europe, Mexico, South America and the United States (Google Online Store, n.d.), the political terrain of these locations affect the store , for example, the political terrain in China wouldn't allow the store to have customers in that location due to the great firewall, hence, the store doesn't deliver to China (Heinze et al., 2016). However, if the political situation in China is replicated in one of the regions being served, then it wouldn't be able to serve the region any longer (Laakso, 2017). Another major political issue is taxation (Jie, Hongwei , & Qifeng , 2015), adding taxes to online merchandises could reduce the rate of purchase by up to 24% (Goolsbee, 2000).

1.2.1.2 Economics

The Covid-19 pandemic has shown that online stores are some of the few businesses that can remain profitable even during economic turmoil (Kim, 2020), however, the economy still impacts online stores (Dedrick, Kenneth, & Nigel, 2006). A decline in the economy could result in reduced purchasing power and vice versa (William, 2007), factors such as inflation and exchange rate directly impact purchasing power (Martikainen, 2014), the economy of a region has also been

shown to impact adoption of information technology and this indirectly impacts purchase from online stores (Dedrick, Kenneth, & Nigel, 2006).

1.2.1.3 Social

Social factors such as age, jobs, migration and even the market structure of a region affect the extent to which an online store can thrive in a region (Ramya & Mohamed, 2016) . The influence of others on a person has been termed subjective norm (Wang, Chen, Chang, & Yang, 2007), it plays a role in buyer acceptance of google merchandises and other online stores (Ajzen & Fishbein, 1980). TRA (The theory of reasoned action) has postulated that subjective norm and beliefs play a role in the buying behaviour of users (Sheppard, Hartwick, & Warshaw, 1988) and therefore the acceptance of certain types of online stores among a social group (Ajzen & Fishbein, 1980).

1.2.1.4 Technology

Technology greatly affects online stores like Google merchandise store (Meegahapola & Perera, 2017). Any technological influence within a region directly influences the store (Thorsten, et al., 2010; Prabuddha De, Mohammad S. Rahman, & Yu, 2010), the more time users spend online the more they are likely to come across the product while searching for activities to perform online (Heinze et al., 2016).

1.2.1.5 Legal

Legal factors influencing Google merchandise store include various regulation, laws, policies and restriction (Heinze, Fletcher, & Rashid, 2016). Taxation laws, importation laws amongst others have an impact on running google merchandise store (Martikainen, 2014), for instance, taxation and importations laws in a certain country might make a product cost more (Lee, 2006), or require that the buyer pays some extra fees to the government after already making payments on the website (Goolsbee, 2000). Even though these online stores are mandated by law to avoid any form

of hidden charges the best they can do in some cases to warn buyers, for example stating that ‘extra charges may apply’ (Lindsay, 2016).

1.2.1.6 Environmental

One major environmental factor impacts the store is consumer environmental awareness (Heinze et al., 2016; Masele, 2011). Consumers are becoming more conscious about environmentally friendly products (Nagaraju & Thejaswini , 2014) and would rather buy recycled, eco-friendly or second-hand products (Laakso, 2017).

1.2.2 Competitive analysis using Porter’s Five Forces Analysis

1.2.2.1 Threat of Substitution

This is a very high impact threat, independent designers and artist produce various google branded products that are sold across various channels both online and offline (Rodney, 2010). The store’s competition aren’t only those offering google branded products (Peteraf & Bergen, 2003), various stores are offering the exact same services for equally popular brands an example is Microsoft Merchandise store, other online stores such as redbubble offer the same products for a variety brands (Nasrin & Muhammad, 2012).

1.2.2.2 Threat of Entry

Various barriers to entry such as supply side economies of scale will lead to more expenses for a new entrant due to higher production costs for smaller volumes considering the fact that new entrants wouldn’t have built enough customer base to enable large production scale (Nasrin & Muhammad, 2012), the existing customer base also presents a low impact of demand side economies of scale because customers like to buy from popular existing brands (Ajzen & Fishbein, 1980); customer switching cost poses as a high impact because in the case of an online store it cost

little to nothing for customers to switch (Alberto, Aguilar-Medina, & Fernández-Caballero, 2018), the high cost of branding – low impact, it would also be very expensive for a new brand to compete against a brand as reputable as Google. Threat of entry can be concluded to be a weak threat to Google merchandise store (Roberta, 2019; Heinze et al.,2016; Porter, 2008)

1.2.2.3 Bargaining Power of Suppliers

This has a strong force, because the suppliers provide the materials with which the products on the website are produced and branded, with a small population of suppliers available this has a high impact on Google merchandise store (Roberta, 2019; Heinze et al.,2016).

1.2.2.4 Bargaining Power of Buyers

This has a strong impact on the store because buyers do not have a means of bargaining the price of products on the website so instead they would visit other websites or brick and mortar stores to get the product at a better rate (Heinze et al.,2016).

1.2.2.5 Competitive Rivalry

This is a very high impact risk and is like the risk of substitution because there exist various online and physical stores offering the services (Roberta, 2019), as well as independent sources of these goods (Rodney, 2010;Heinze et al.,2016). Some existing online rivals are Microsoft merchandise store, Redbubble and iLogo.

1.2.3 Buyer Persona

Buyer personas are a key part of determining effective strategies and goals of a business, and content as an internal capability (Heinze et al.,2016). Based on analytics data (Google Analytics Google Merchandise Store, 2020) a buyer persona has been built (see Appendix C).

1.2.4 Market Trends

One major market trend is extended reality (Marion & Ingrid, 2019), it improves user experience and improve information access during purchase (Philipp & Katrin, 2014). Data insights also show that most user access information from their mobile devices (Google Analytics Google Merchandise Store, 2020; IBM Corporation, 2020), this shows that the store would perform better with a mobile first orientation – a mobile application (Max-Emanuel, Hausen, & De Luca, 2010).

1.2.5 Key Influencers

Based on analytics data (Google Analytics Google Merchandise Store, 2020) and buyer persona (see Appendix C), the key influencers have been identified to be movie stars, technology gadgets influencers and bloggers (Mohit , 2011), because analytics data shows that most of the store customers are technophiles and movie lovers (Google Analytics Google Merchandise Store, 2020).

1.3 Internal Capabilities

1.3.1 Digital Channels

The store currently utilises digital channels, with the presence of its store on the web and optimisation for search engine (Anthony, Erika, & Kimara, 2014), the current high search engine rank of the store makes it easy to be found by users on the web (Turban, King, Lee, Liang, & Turban, 2015). This is highly advantageous because of the communication shift that has occurred between businesses and customers, the business power has shifted from organisations to the customers (Thorsten, et al., 2010), with digital media, customers trust peers and information available on the web more than organisations (Deloitte Touche Tohmatsu Limited , 2014), hence, perception of an organisation is based on the information that can be found across the web

(Greenberg, 2009; Weber, 2009). However, the store isn't utilising some other digital channels (Bala & Verma, 2018), this has led to the store being impersonated on social media.

1.3.2 Data

The store currently has a google analytics dashboard, this provides insights into user data (Google Analytics Google Merchandise Store, 2020). This is a major strength for the store because data insights lead to value creation and helps with creating an effective strategy (IBM Corporation, 2020), being linked to the google brand gives the store access to data beyond what is available on the analytics dashboard, this knowledge of its users and their behaviour even outside of the store is a strength for the store, there are many benefits provided by access of knowledge and mined data (Juhnyoung, Mark, Schonberg , & Robert , 2001).

1.3.3 Content

The store's content focuses primarily on its merchandise, with nice features like social media and email sharing, pdf download of content, printing of content. The content of the store is also customised based on user location (Google Online Store, n.d.). However, the content could be more engaging if a reviews section was added, a reviews section would build customer trust in the product quality (Greenberg, 2009; Weber, 2009). Consumer driven content is a very important part of the success of any online business (Deloitte Touche Tohmatsu Limited , 2014).

1.4 SWOT Analysis

SWOT analysis, is a component of the digital marketing strategic planning process which was developed by Harvard Business School in the 1960s, it analyses internal factors: strength and weaknesses of the organisation, and external factors influencing an organisation: opportunities and threats; so that strategic choices can be made towards the implementation of the digital marketing

strategy (Heinze et al.,2016; Gurel & Tat, 2017; Al-Araki,2013). The SWOT analysis has been argued to be an ineffective tool of situational analysis, with many researchers such as Pickton and Wright (1998) labelling it as a ‘naïve’ tool, and Al-Akari (2013) describing it as inefficient because of its top-down approach of data gathering, nevertheless, other researchers like Thompson et al. (2007) have argued that SWOT analysis is a powerful tool despite its simplicity, ultimately it has become quite a popular situational analysis tool (Fisher, Chrispin, & Fisher, 2000) and it has simplified the process of Situational analysis.

Table 1 shows the SWOT analysis in relation to internal and external factors.

1.4.1 Strength

The store offers a catalogue of google branded products online; therefore, it operates everywhere, every time, because of this its customers are from around the globe, and can shop at any hour of the day and any day of the year (Fisher et al., 2000). A significant strength of the store is that it is built on a reputable brand (Ramya & Mohamed, 2016) , it allows for easy product search and an attractive display, eases the stress of travel and saves travel resources (Muhammad & Tanzila, 2012). The variety of contents available on the website is a strength (Tsaka, Kastelli, & Yannis, 2004), because it attracts both individuals and businesses, while the store caters to individuals in most sections of the website, the souvenir section is more suited for businesses as they can get branded items for their events (Google Online Store, n.d.). Access to data is a strength for the store (Deloitte Touche Tohmatsu Limited , 2014), it’s access to a google data, which gives insight into user behaviour and trends that can help the store predict user buying activities. The high search engine rank of the store is a strength because it helps the store to be found easily (Juhnyoung, Mark,

Schonberg , & Robert , 2001), the store's content is customised based on user location, customisation improves user experience (Gerti, Birgit, Werner , & Wieland , 2003).

1.4.2 Weakness

One of the most obvious weaknesses of the store is that it isn't utilising its brand optimally (Greenberg, 2009), google is a brand known by almost every internet user, however, this store isn't known to many and seems almost mysterious to some people. Like most online stores there are security concerns for a lot of customers, as well as concerns regarding quality, personalisation and fit of products (Fisher et al., 2000; Muhammad & Tanzila,2012; Martikainen,2014).

1.4.3 Opportunity

The porter's five forces analysis has identified competition and substitution to be major threats to the store, moving ahead with technology can set Google merchandise store ahead of its competition (Anderson, 1997). The google merchandise store doesn't have a mobile application, mobile applications have become widely accepted e-commerce medium, a mobile technology stack will be highly beneficial to the store (Muhammad & Tanzila,2012). The PESTLE analysis also identified technology and social issues as having impact on the buyer behaviour (Ajzen & Fishbein, 1980), however, modern technologies have given room to improved user experience that has been termed extended reality (Robert-Edia & Yahaya, 2022) (Meegahapola & Perera, 2017). Ikea implemented an augmented reality catalogue which helps buyers to see how well a purchase would fit into their space, a similar model can be adapted in google online stores apparel section, extended reality would enable buyers have a more realistic view of the product, online customisation features would enable buyers personalise the products to their taste (Marion & Ingrid, 2019)

1.4.4 Threat

Multiple threats have been identified in the PESTLE analysis, some of these threats include, laws, taxes and other regulations that hinder the operations of the online store, competition is also a major threat, the porter's analysis has identified competitive rivalry to be a high impact threat to the store (Dedrick et al.,2006; Lindsay, 2016).

2.0 SMART Objectives

2.1 Literature Review

SMART objective was introduced by Doran (1981), as a means for developing effective management goals, today, it is being used across various fields beyond management (Preskill & Boyle, 2008). In SMART framework, objectives are developed based on Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Realistic and Time bound indicators (BrittBjerke & Renger, 2017; Doran, 1981; Hofman & Hofman,2011; Heinze et al., 2016).

Some authors have argued that the one fits all approach of SMART can be inaccurate because it is being used to justify activities performed instead being part of the planning process (Grudens-Schuck, 2003), however, the context in which the framework work is used determines it's applicability and accuracy (BrittBjerke & Renger, 2017;Williams & Hawkes, 2003). According to BrittBjerke & Renger (2017) there are several advantages of mainstreaming SMART objectives and alternative methods of developing them can be key to accuracy, to meet the criteria it is very important for the objective to include a completeion date.Mainstreaming of the framework should be carried out taking into account the context of application and with insight into the baseline for creating the objectives (BrittBjerke & Renger, 2017).

2.2 SMART Objectives of Google merchandise store

According to the SOSTAC process (Chaffey, 2012), making use of the findings from the situational analysis, objectives were set (see Table 2) based on the SMART framework (Heinze et al., 2016; BrittBjerke & Renger, 2017; Doran, 1981).

- Smart Objective 1: Use social media to improve customer engagement, trust and store popularity, through reviews, gifts and promotions in 3 months.
- Smart Objective 2: Build upon the existing google brand to make the store more popular with 6 months.
- Smart Objective 3: Add user review feature to the website and encourage user to interact with the feature within 1 year.

2.3 Strategic Recommendations

Strategic recommendations have been developed for the first year based on the buyer persona spring strategy template (see Appendix A).

- Recommendation 1: Social Media engagement and followership of at least 1000 followers on each platform in 3 months. To achieve this, social media channels – Facebook, Instagram, Twitter and TikTok would be used (Peter, Peter, Peter, & Freundt, 2014), because the buyer persona uses social media platforms, contents like discussions about latest technology trends, discussions about new merchandise and designs, promotions and discounts should be used , because the buyer persona is interested in technology trends, is a technophile and the analytics data has shown that the buyer persona is a value shopper (Google Analytics Google Merchandise Store, 2020).

- Recommendation 2: Increase site visits by 100% in 6 months using Google platforms as a means to generate traffic, because the buyer persona interacts with google platforms and has a level of trust for the brand, using key words and ad words like discounts would also increase click rates because the buyer persona is a value shopper, users are technologically inclined, spending most of their time interacting with various technological tools, even google products utilising google platforms would be effective (Google Analytics Google Merchandise Store, 2020).
- Recommendation 3: Have over 100 customer reviews on the website within 1 year. Various analysis have shown that users enjoy generating content on the web and they trust peers more than organisations (Weber, 2009;Google Analytics Google Merchandise Store, 2020), this is particularly applicable to the store because a review feature would help build customer trust in the store and its products (Deloitte Touche Tohmatsu Limited , 2014).

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Tables

Table 1: SWOT Analysis

INTERNAL FACTORS	EXTERNAL FACTORS
<p>Strengths</p> <p>The customers are from all over the world, there are no geographic restrictions for business transactions.</p> <p>Round the clock operating hours.</p> <p>Built upon a globally recognised brand name- Google.</p> <p>Low cost of business operations.</p> <p>Attractive Product display.</p> <p>Ease of shopping, as customers do not have to travel to shop and products can be delivered to them.</p>	<p>Opportunities</p> <p>Mobile technology stack. (Yahaya, 2022)</p> <p>Extended reality using technologies such as 360 degrees view, 3-D runways, virtual and augmented reality.</p> <p>User customisation of products.</p> <p>Advertising</p> <p>Size Chart, for improved shopping experience.</p> <p>Customer Reviews Feature</p>

<p>Location based online shopping personalisation.</p> <p>Branded products.</p> <p>Access to data</p>	
<p>Weaknesses</p> <p>Security risks like phishing.</p> <p>Customer trust concerns.</p> <p>Poor customer experience in terms of deciding if an apparel is appropriate.</p> <p>Unpopular online store despite being built upon a popular brand name.</p> <p>Due lack of social media presence, some individuals have created potential scam accounts with the store name across various social media platforms.</p>	<p>Threats</p> <p>There are independent designers selling the exact same product at lower rates.</p> <p>There are substitute brands available, an example is Microsoft merchandise store.</p>

Table 2: SMART Objectives

Objective 1	Use social media to improve customer engagement, trust and store popularity, through reviews, gifts and promotions.			
Justification	Certain individuals are using the store name, thereby reducing trust in the store and competitors are gaining traction from social media and even selling the merchandise on social media.			
Specific	Measurable	Achievable	Realistic	Time Bound
Improve social media engagement and followership.	Track social media followership and post engagement, and store visits referred from	Social media contents and Ad Campaigns	Facebook, Instagram, twitter as well as other social media platforms have billions of users and run	3 months

Objective 1	Use social media to improve customer engagement, trust and store popularity, through reviews, gifts and promotions.			
	social media through referrer links.		campaign Ads at a fee	
Objective 2	Build upon the existing google brand to make the store more popular			
Justification	The SWOT analysis identifies that a major weakness of the store is that it isn't as popular as expected given the brand name.			
Specific	Measurable	Achievable	Realistic	Time Bound
Increase site visits	Track click rate from google analytics dashboard	Use call to actions attract new users	Google has billions of users across their various platforms (Liu, 2020).	6 months
Objective 3	Add user review feature to the website			
Justification	User reviews improves trust in a brand (Deloitte Touche Tohmatsu Limited , 2014)			
Specific	Measurable	Achievable	Realistic	Time Bound
Add user review feature to the website	Track engagements	Review products purchased	The store is web based and its features can be extended	1 year

Appendices

Appendix A: Buyer Persona Spring Strategy

Strategic business objective for 3/5 years	Channels	Content	Strategic Keyword Terms	KPIs	Buyer persona		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Social Media engagement and followership of at least 1000 followers on each platform in 3 months. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Social media channels – Facebook, Instagram, Twitter and TikTok 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Discussions about latest technology trends. Discussions on about new merchandise and designs. Promotions and discounts. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> #FOMO #giveaways #google #discount Google Merchandise #techie #branded Branded Items 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Facebook Likes Instagram followers Twitter followers Post comments on Instagram and Facebook Post reactions on Instagram and Facebook Post retweet on twitter Website referral from social media 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A technophile who loves the google brand and is a value Shopper 		
Strategy implementation plan – key activities and next deadlines							
Plan:	30-June-2020	Act:	07-July-2020	Observe:	21-August-2020	Reflect:	03-September-2020

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Risk Assessment • Create social media pages • Verify social media accounts • Create posts using relevant keywords and hashtags 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Employ a social media manager • Reach out to social media platforms to verify account • Provide all requirements for verified social media accounts • Research on relevant contents and hashtags for buyer persona • Develop contents relevant to buyer persona • Monitor competitor social media activities and trends 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engagement level based on content type • Followership and rate of unfollowing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monthly review meetings • Review the rate of success keywords and KPIs. • Review accuracy of buyer persona • Review accuracy of key influencers
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Strategic business objective for 3/5 years	Channels	Content	Strategic Keyword Terms	KPIs	Buyer persona
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<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase site visits by 100% in 6 months 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Google platforms including chrome browser, search engine, e-mail. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promotions and discounts. • Links and shortcuts to store. • AdWords 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • google • discount • Google Merchandise • Branded Items 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Track click rate from google analytics dashboard 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A technophile who loves the google brand and is a user of google products
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Strategy implementation plan – key activities and next deadlines

Plan:	30-June-2020	Act:	30-July-2020	Observe:	30-November-2020	Reflect:	30-November-2020
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Risk Assessment • Create Content 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reach out Google to add shortcut and links to the store on their platforms. • Monitor click rates from google analytics dashboard 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Click through rate 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quarterly review meetings • Review the rate of success AdWords • Review accuracy of buyer persona 	

Strategic business objective for 3/5 years		Channels	Content	Strategic Keyword Terms		KPIs	Buyer persona
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Have over 100 customer reviews on the website within 1 year 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The store website 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> User driven content 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Review 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Track number of reviews on the website 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A technophile who loves the google brand and buys products from the store
Strategy implementation plan – key activities and next deadlines							
Plan:	30- June-2020	Act:	07- December-2020	Observe:	21-April- 2021	Reflect:	03- May-2020
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Risk Assessment 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Extend the website to include customer reviews 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Customer engagement 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Monthly review meetings 	

Appendix B: Risk Assessment

Risk Identification	1 (Low) to 5(High)			Mitigations /Further Actions
	Probability	Impact	Gross risk	
Not being well received by the social media community	5	5	25	Study current social media trends, run a pilot based on that, based on pilot results proceed or recreate social media plan.
Google refusing to add short cut to the store on their platforms	1	3	3	Pitch to Google that the popularity of the merchandise would increase trust in the brand.
Users ignoring shortcut to the store if it is added on google platforms	3	4	12	Study user behaviour across devices, based on this data, revisit the plan
Customers refusing to review their purchases on the website	1	5	5	Encourage users to review purchases through reward points.
Customers submitting only negative reviews on the website	3	5	15	Produce high quality product and ensure the best customer service.